

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Teaching Programmes on Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Organ Donation among Non-Health Professional Students at Selected College, Hosur

Mrs. Janet Rose.¹, Mrs. B. GOWRI, M.Sc., (N)², Dr. Mrs. R. JAMUNARANI, M.Sc (N)., Ph.D³

¹J - Reg. No-301912652 Master of Science In Nursing, Medical Surgical Nursing (Critical Care Nursing) Sresakthimayeil Institute of Nursing And Research, Namakkal

²Reader, HOD, Medical-Surgical Nursing, Sresakthimayeil Institute of Nursing & Research, (JKK Nataraja Educational Institutions), Kumarapalayam, Namakkal District.

³Principal, Sresakthimayeil Institute of Nursing & Research, (JKK Nataraja Educational Institutions), Kumarapalayam, Namakkal District.

ABSTRACT

India is currently having a deceased donation rate of 0.05–0.08 per million population. The National Organ and Tissue Transplant Programme have planned strategies to improve organ donation by creating awareness and capacity building. There is a great need to assess the knowledge regarding organ donation among the general population. In our community, so many myths and misconceptions people have regarding organ donation. This prevents people to come forward to donate their organs whenever the need arises. When we educate and motivate the student population they will not only donate their organs but also motivate others also to donate their organs to form a very healthy society. Hence, this study has been undertaken to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding organ donation among college students as they are going to be tomorrow's responsible citizens of our nation. The objectives of the study were to assess the pre-test and post-test levels of knowledge and attitude, to assess the effectiveness of Video-assisted teaching, to find out the association between post-test levels of knowledge and attitude, and to assess the correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding organ Donation. The research design used was a pre-experimental group pre-test and post-test design. The data collection tool was validated by General Physician and the four Nursing experts. Reliability was established by the test-retest method, $r = 0.8$ for the structured knowledge questionnaire and 0.87 for the attitude rating scale. The samples for the study were chosen by using the purposive sampling technique, and 40 samples were selected. Data was collected by using a structured knowledge questionnaire and an attitude rating scale. Data was collected for a period of one month. The data collected were edited, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted manually. The obtained overall post-test Mean for knowledge was 24.37, SD 7.8, and for attitude Post-the test Mean was 23 SD 6.56. The obtained mean difference for knowledge was 17.62 and the attitude was 6 and the paired-test value for knowledge was 13.15 for knowledge and for attitude it was 4.47 significant at the level of $P < 0.05$. The demographic variables Residential area, Sources of information regarding organ donation, and the persons to whom you are willing to donate were associated with post-test scores on knowledge, and the demographic variables Sex, residential area, and persons whom you are willing to donate were associated with the post-test scores on attitude. Other demographic variables were not significant with the post-test scores on knowledge and attitude. The study's findings revealed that there was a significant difference in pre-test and post-test scores on the level of knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation and a significant association between the post-test level of knowledge and attitude with their selected demographic variables.

KEYWORDS: Organ Donation, Non-Health Professionals, Video-assisted teaching, Attitude, Knowledge,

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
17 March 2023

Available on:
<https://ijmscr.org/>

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Teaching Programmes on Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Organ Donation among Non-Health Professional Students at Selected College, Hosur

INTRODUCTION

Organ donation is the process when a person allows an organ of their own to be removed and transplanted to another person, legally, either by consent while the donor is alive or dead with the assent of the next of kin. Human organ donation was legalized in India in 1994 through “The Transplantation of Human Organs Act” which is accepted by all the states except Andhra and Jammu Kashmir. The act aims to regulate the removal, storage, and, transplantation of human organs for therapeutic purposes and prevent commercial dealings in human organs. Organ donors are usually dead at the time of donation but may be living. For living donors, organ donation typically involves extensive testing before the donation, including psychological evaluation to determine whether the would-be donor understands and consents to the donation.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the pre-test and post-test level of knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation among non-health professional students.
2. To assess the effectiveness of video-assisted teaching on knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation among non-health professional students.
3. To find out the association between post-test level of knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation and the selected demographic variables among non-health professional students.
4. To assess the correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding organ Donation.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

METHODOLOGY

Research approach: - Quantitative Evaluative approach is used to assess video-assisted teaching as an effective way to improve the knowledge of non-health professional students

HYPOTHESIS

- H₁:** There was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test levels of knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation among non-health professional students.
- H₂:** There was a significant association between the post-test level of knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation and their selected demographic variables among non-health professional students.
- H₃:** There was a significant correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation.

ASSUMPTIONS

- ❑ Non-health professional students may have inadequate knowledge regarding organ donation.
- ❑ Video-assisted teaching is an effective way to improve the knowledge of Non- health professional students regarding organ donation.
- ❑ Non health professional students also can serve society to improve the health and living standard of the people by donating their organs.
- ❑ Knowledge regarding organ donation can create a positive attitude to donate organs.
- ❑ Knowledge regarding organ donation can help the Non - health professional students to understand the rumors, myths, misconceptions, and facts regarding organ donation.

regarding organ donation students studying B.A. English III year at Government Arts and Science College, Hosur.

Research Design: -Pre-experimental with one group pre- test and post-test design.

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Teaching Programmes on Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Organ Donation among Non-Health Professional Students at Selected College, Hosur

Research Setting: - Government Arts and Science College, Midugarapalli, Hosur.

Independent Variables: Video Assisted Teaching regarding organ donation.

□ VARIABLES –

Dependent Variables: Knowledge and Attitude regarding organ donation.

Sample Size: - The sample size for this study was arbitrarily decided to be 40.

Sample Techniques: - Purposive sampling method.

Fig. 3.1: SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

POPULATION

Target Population: A Total membership of a defined set of samples is selected and to whom the data will be generalized. In this study, the target populations were Non-health professional students.

Accessible Population: the students belong to BA (English) third year at Government Arts and Science College, Midugarapalli Road, Amman Nagar, Hosur.

□ SAMPLING CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria:

- ❖ Students who are willing to participate.
- ❖ Students who are present on the day of data collection.
- ❖ Students including males and females.
- ❖ Students who know to read, write, and understand English.
- ❖ Students only in BA final year English Major.

Exclusion Criteria

- ❖ Students who are not willing to participate.
- ❖ Students who are sick.
- ❖ Students who are absent on the day of data collection.
- ❖ Students in other departments except for English Major.
- ❖ Students in PG English major.

- ❖ Students who are exposed to any teaching program related to organ donation in the past.

DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH TOOL

Part – A: Socio-demographic variables

Part – B: Knowledge questionnaire regarding organ donation

Part – C: Attitude Rating Scale

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

- ❖ **Phase I:** Screening Phase
- ❖ **Phase II:** Data collection & Implementation Phase
- ❖ **Phase III:** Termination Phase

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

□ Findings were presented in the forms of tables, and diagrams under the following sections: The data analyzed were presented as follows:

Section - I: Data on selected demographic variables of non-health professional students who participated in the study

Section - II: Data on pre and post-test level of knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation among non-health professional students.

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Teaching Programmes on Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Organ Donation among Non-Health Professional Students at Selected College, Hosur

Section - III: Data on the effectiveness of video-assisted teaching program regarding organ donation among non-health professional students.

Section - IV: Data on the association between post-test level of knowledge and attitude and the selected demographic variables among non-health professional students

Section - V: Data on the correlation between the post-test level of knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation among non-health professional students

SECTION – I

Frequency and percentage distribution of pre –test and post -test level of knowledge regarding organ donation among non-health professional students

S. No	Test	Inadequate knowledge		Moderately adequate knowledge		Adequate knowledge		Total number of samples	
		Freq	Per	Freq	Per	Freq	Per	Freq	Per
1.	Pre test	36	90%	4	10%	0	0	40	100%
2.	Post test	6	15%	20	50%	14	35%	40	100%

SECTION – II

Frequency and percentage distribution of samples according to pre and post test scores on attitude regarding organ donation among non -health professional students

S.No	Test	Positive Attitude		Negative Attitude		Total number of samples	
		Freq	Per	Freq	Per	Freq	Per
1.	Pretest	15	37.5%	25	62.5%	40	100%
2.	Post test	30	75%	10	25%	40	100%

SECTION – III

S. No.	Experimental Group	Mean	SD	Range	Mean difference	Paired “t” value
1.	Pre test	6.75	3.3	2-14	17.62	t = 13.15 Df = 39 P <0.05 Significant
2.	Post test	24.37	7.8	10-35		

SECTION – IV

Frequency and percentage distribution of pre –test and post -test level of knowledge regarding organ donation among non-health professional students

S. No.	Experimental Group	Mean	SD	Range	Mean difference	Paired “t” value
1.	Pre test	17	5.18	10-25	6	t = 4.47 Df=39 P<0.05 Significant
2.	Post test	23	6.56	10-33		

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Teaching Programmes on Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Organ Donation among Non-Health Professional Students at Selected College, Hosur

SECTION – V

Correlation between post- test levels of knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation

Post test	Mean	SD	“r” value
Knowledge	24.37	7.8	r = 0.46
Attitude	23	6.56	

FINDINGS

I. Findings related to selected demographic variables of the students who participated in the study

- ❖ Majority of the participants 22(55%) were between 17-18 years of age, 27(67.50%) were females, 25(32.50%) were staying in rural, 30 (75%) were Hindu, 28(70%) coming from Nuclear family,19(47.50%) heard about organ donation through media,25(62.50%) said they had thought of donating organ in the past, 15(37.50%) said that they have to discuss with the family members to donate their organ in the future, 22(55%) said they will donate their organ only to their family members, 33(82.50%) were interested in deceased donation.

II. Findings on pre and post-test scores on knowledge and attitude regarding organ donation among the students who participated in the study.

- ❖ It was inferred that among 40 participants in the pre-test, 36 (90%) had inadequate knowledge and 4 (10%) had moderately adequate knowledge and no one had adequate knowledge. The post-test was administered after Video Assisted Teaching regarding organ donation. In the post-test, the majority of them 20 (50%) gained adequate knowledge and 14 (35%) had moderately adequate knowledge and six (15%) were there in the category of inadequate knowledge which showed that Video Assisted Teaching was effective. The post-test knowledge scores showed a significant difference.
- ❖ It was inferred that in the pre-test majority 25 (62.50%) had negative attitudes and only 15 (37.50%) had positive attitudes. After Video-Assisted teaching majority 30(75%) changed their attitude from negative to positive and only 10(25%) showed a negative attitude toward organ donation. It shows that an increase in knowledge promotes a positive attitude regarding organ donation.

III. Findings on the effectiveness of the Video-Assisted Teaching Programme on organ donation among the students who participated in the study.

- ❖ In pre- test the obtained overall mean score was 6.75, SD 3.3 whereas in post- test the obtained overall mean score was 24.37, SD 7.8 and the mean difference was 17.62 and the paired t test value was 13.15 which is significant at the level of $P < 0.05$ showed that there was a significant increase in the knowledge after the video-assisted teaching on organ donation.
- ❖ It was inferred that there was a significant improvement in the level of knowledge after the video-assisted teaching program regarding organ donation. Hence the

video-assisted teaching program was effective among the students who participated in the study.

- ❖ The obtained overall mean score in the pre-test was 17, SD 5.18, in the post- test the obtained overall mean score was 23, SD 6.56 and the mean difference was 6 and the paired t test value was 4.47.
- ❖ It was inferred that post test score was significantly increased than the pre-test scores. Therefore, it was inferred that the Video-assisted teaching program was effective in changing the attitude of non-health professional students regarding organ donation.

IV. Findings on the association between post-test scores on knowledge with their selected demographic variables among the students who participated in the study

- ❖ It was inferred that the selected demographic variable such as Residential area, Sources of information regarding organ donation, and significant with the post Persons to whom you are willing to donate was significant with post-test score on knowledge at the level of 0.05. Other demographic variables such as age, sex, religion, Type of family, thought of organ donation in the past, willingness to donate organ in the future, timing of donating organ were not significant with the post-test score on knowledge at the level of 0.05.
- ❖ It was inferred that the selected demographic variable such as Sex, Residential area, Persons whom you are willing to donate were significant with post test score on attitude at the level of 0.05. Other demographic variables such as age, religion, Type of family, Sources of information regarding organ donation, thought of organ donation in the past, willingness to donate organ in the future, timing of donating organ were not significant with the post-tests score on knowledge at the level of 0.05.

V. Findings on correlation between post-test scores on knowledge and attitude among the students participated in the study

- ❖ The post -test knowledge mean was 24.37 with SD 7.8 and the attitude Mean was 23 with SD 6.56 and the r value was 0.46 calculated by Karl Pearson correlation coefficient method. It was found to be positively correlated. Hence, it was inferred that when the knowledge was increased, attitude also changed.

NURSING IMPLICATIONS

Nursing Service

- ❖ The nurses are in the best position to give more awareness about organ donation, and need to take up the

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Teaching Programmes on Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Organ Donation among Non-Health Professional Students at Selected College, Hosur

responsibility to create awareness regarding organ donation.

Nursing Administration

- ❖ Organ donation is a growing needy problem. More emphasis should be given to the condition. Cost effective production of material used for teaching by nurses should be encouraged. Necessary administrative support, proper procedure counselling should be providing to conduct such activities.

Nursing Education

- ❖ The study has been proved that knowledge and attitude on organ donation among undergraduate students can improve their attitude and knowledge to community.
- ❖ Our nursing personal need to be equipped and with adequate knowledge regarding the organ donation through the types of donation of organ, benefit, criteria, procurement process, donor evaluation criteria, organ allocation, registration, registries, caste of donor and recipient.
- ❖ Nursing personal looking in various health setting should be given in service education to update their knowledge, attitude and abilities to identifying the learning needs of clients on organ donation and planning for appropriate intervention.

Nursing Research

- ❖ The finding for the study can be utilized to conduct. It is essential to identify at present level of knowledge of individual regarding organ donation to know the extent of information necessary to be given and disseminated.
- ❖ This study motivates the other to conduct further studies on organ donation.
- ❖ The study also brings about the fact that more studies need to be done at different setting which are culturally acceptable with better teaching strategies of education.

LIMITATIONS

The study is limited to those who are willing to participate.
The study is limited to only 40 samples.
The study is limited to only one college.
The study is limited to 3rd year Students of B.A English department of Government arts and science college, Hosur
The study is limited to the period of 4 weeks.
The study is limited to video assisted teaching.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A comparative study can be done to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching Programme on urban and rural area.
A similar study can be conducted in large scale sample.
The study can be done in the hospitals, schools and industrial settings.

CONCLUSION

The current study revealed the marked deficit in knowledge and negative attitude about organ donation in study population. The introduction of the subject in early age, clarification of doubts by organizing public health education programs at various institutions like schools, colleges, health centers, various working institutions and hospitals may help in building knowledge base and positive attitude towards donation of organs which will in turn meet the needs of organs and save many lives.

Hence Health care workers especially nurse and medical social workers may prove to be precious assets to spread the word about organ donation in hospitals as well as community health centers.

REFERENCES – BOOKS

- I. Basavanthappa, B.T. (2003). "Medical Surgical Nursing", 1st edition, New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers.
- II. Kothari, C.R. (2004). "Research Methodology methods and Techniques". New Delhi: New Age International Publishers. (Original work published 1985).
- III. Pamela G Reed, Nelna B Crawford, "Perspective on Nursing Theory", 5th edition Published by Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.
- IV. Monahan, Sands, Neighbors, Marek, Green Phipps, "Medical surgical nursing", 8th edition, Published by Mosby Elsevier.
- V. Nicki, R. Colledge., Brian, R. Walker., & Stuart, H. Raltson. (2010). "Davidson's Principles and Practice of Medicine", 21st edition, Churchill Livingstone Elsevier.
- VI. Suresh K Sharma. "Nursing Research and statistics". 1st Edition. India: Elsevier Publishers; 2011.
- VII. Suzanne, C. Smeltzer., & Brenda, G. Bare. (2007). "The Text Book of Medical Surgical Nursing", 12th edition, New York: Lippincott Publications.
- VIII. Thomson, J.M. (1997). "Medical Surgical Nursing". Mosby Publication
- IX. Veer Bala Restogi. "Fundamentals of Biostatistics" Data analysis. New Delhi: Ane books India; 2008.

REFERENCES – JOURNALS

- I. Beenish Fathima P, Arber S, Tyler M. The organ donor crisis: the missed organ donor potential from the accident and emergency departments. Transplantation Proceedings. 2019; 40:1008±11.
- II. Bellali T, Papadatou D. Parental grief following the brain death of a child: does consent or refusal to organ donation affect their grief? Death Studies. 2006; 30: 883±917.

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Teaching Programmes on Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Organ Donation among Non-Health Professional Students at Selected College, Hosur

- III. Donal Mc Glade, Foulkrod KH, Dworaczy K S, Thompson K, Elliot E, Cooper H, Coop wood B. Barriers to obtaining family consent for potential organ donors. *Journal of Trauma-Injury Infection & Critical Care*. 2019; 68:447±51.
- IV. Gokul Sarveswaran, *et.al.*, Are medical students having enough knowledge about organ donation. *IOSR J Dental Med Sci*. 2018;14(7):29–34.
- V. Navdeep Bansal, Qureshi A, Jilani BN, Zehra N. Knowledge and ethical perception regarding organ donation among medical students. *BMC Med Ethics*. 2019;14:38.
- VI. Papadatou D, Bellali T,. The decision-making process of parents regarding organ donation of their brain dead child: A Greek study. *Social Science and Medicine*. 2007; 64: 439 ± 50.
- VII. Sourabh Paul, Chambers SK. Information sources, donation knowledge, and attitudes toward transplant recipients in Australia. *Prog Transplant*. 2019; 24:169–177. doi: 10.7182/pit2014799. - DOI – PubMed .